

Wearable Forest

Smart Fashion Design to Feel a Belonging to Nature

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Abstract: Japanese Zen Buddhism encourages deep meditation in order to achieve a sense of being one with nature. Singing birds, buzzing insects, sounds of leaves gently swaying, and the trickling sound of water in a beautiful forest are all integral to helping us feel at one with Nature. By distancing ourselves from the flurries of modern life and holding a reverent attitude toward Nature, we can start searching for a way to sustainability; coping with nature and our modern life. Wearable Forest is a functional dress which interacts bio-acoustically with a remote forest which is located to the uninhabited subtropical forest of the southern Ryukyu Islands, Japan. The clothing contains two paper-thin speakers embroidered on both front shoulders, 256 pieces of white colored LEDs (Light Emitting Diode) sewn with the conductive thread and sleeve-shaped textile sensors inside the fabric. An embedded CPU system receives the live soundscape data from the remote forest wirelessly; which quantizes the bio-acoustical activity of the wildlife from the data, and visualizes the result as glows through the array of the LEDs. In order to interact with the wildlife, users touch the textile sensor. This describes a new interactive wearable system that creates a sense of unity between users and a remote soundscape.

Key words: *Smart Fashion, e-textile, soundscape, healing fashion, human interface.*

1. Introduction

The advancement of recent science and technology introduces the possibility of bringing new expression into fashion. The fashion designer used to sensing trends, expresses it as a unique wardrobe. Most of the time, the work is conceptual as well as artistic and sensitively catches the edge of the age. Therefore, it is thought that most people's sympathy can be obtained, and thus trendy fashion is produced. Science and technology also feels the flow of the age, and has changed people's life and sense of values. It is greatly similar to fashion in catching the edge of the age. Thus, fashion and technology always sensitively catch and express the flow and the direction of the age.

Also, the expression of clothes has changed greatly up to now due to the development of new material by the advancement of science and technology. In the future, it is expected that new clothes will be created that exceed people's imagination by the development of e-textiles --the integration of electronics and textile for functional fabrics.

The authors are researching clothes with the function of Smart Fashion as a new form of expression. Smart Fashion that the authors are advocating differs from "computers that can be worn" known as Wearable Computers, and has aimed to achieve "clothes with functionality." This adds technology to improve the expression and the function of clothes while keeping the essence of usual clothes. In this paper, one example of Smart Fashion is shown by reporting the work of "Wearable Forest -- a cloth generating a feeling of belonging to nature" that the authors have developed. Technology is verified and the expression of fashion is enriched.

The composition of this paper is as follows. Section 2 introduces some works shown in past Paris Collections and the designer's collection as cases where the technology is integrated into fashion as a new expression and the research of the basic technology of e-textile. Section 3 introduces the concept of Wearable Forest, and the main discourse of the system of Wearable Forest is brought together. Conclusions are discussed in section 4.

2. Related Work

2.1. Related Fashion Work

Cases of fashion and technology are described in this section. The works quoted here technically change the silhouette and the luster of clothes as the expression of new clothes. The work that unites the mechanical technology with clothes is announced in Hussein Chalayan's Spring/Summer Paris Collection. The collection work that made looking back on the history of the dress from 1895 to the present is shown here. The transition of fashion to clothes is evident and the transformation of silhouettes is expressed while wearing actual clothes. Specifically, a small motor is used multiple times and the pattern of the skirt length and the collar and silhouettes have been changed. Similarly, clothes that have the motif of an airplane were announced in the collection of Autumn/Winter 2007. [2] Moreover in the Spring/Summer collection in 2008, the work "Laser dresses" was introduced that combines the laser light with the motor. [3] This is a conceptual work with the aim of expressing the celebrity by emitting strong laser light like sunshine.

Yohji Yamamoto introduced his work in the Autumn/Winter collection 2007. [15] The work features flamenco style dot skirts with an autonomous rotation function which emphasizes rich draping.

Angel Chang announced the casual dresses in 2007 which changes color by changing temperature in the atmosphere using textile coated temperature ink or LED worn coats as accessories. [4]

In the fashion in 2003 in which the first author collaborated with ballet, the fiber textile and LED were combined and the lighting of LED was controlled by tying together the two dancers' hands. Also Marie with more than 100 LED is introduced for trial for integrating technology and fashion shown as Figure 1[13].

Figure.1 Media Fashion Show

2.2. Related Study

In this section, related work of smart fashion and research issues of e-textiles are introduced. In related work, smart fashion prototypes which uses the emotional change or behaviour as fashion design are introduced. In research issue of e-textiles, lighting technology which integrates textile and electronics are introduced.

Stead et al. [11] translate emotional status into the colour of a cloth for evaluating a new expression. They think that cloth is a boundary between a person and society and an added function of poetic expression to express the positive and negative emotions of people.

Berzowska et al.[1] evaluate the possibility of a cloth as a medium which records physical communication or behaviour. Specifically, they visualize a touched log using a temperature ink printed cloth. If someone touches the surface of the cloth, the touched area changes colour according to his/her temperature. In another prototype, the sensor suit captures a person's physical motion using acceleration sensors, each of which has full colour LED changing the lighting condition by sensor output.

Dias et al. [5] conduct fundamental research about electronic circuits using conductive thread for illumination. They developed emitting knit using EL polymer thread when giving high voltage.

Phillips Co. Ltd. in Holland developed an LED integrated e-textile called Lumalive[10]. Lumalive is used for adding display function to any fashion items such as cloth, accessory and interior. The characteristic of Lumalive is its fibre structure to diffuse LED light effectively. Though there are some problems to be solved until it is commercially available such as stiffness of the textile and expandability of the system, Lumalive will attract the attention of the fashion industry.

3. Wearable Forest

3.1. Wearable Forest Concept

Wearable Forest is a cloth to feel a belonging to nature. To maintain human civilization, man requires a breakthrough in his relationship with nature, which has been destroyed in the process of urbanization. However, the nature conservation movement, which promotes conservation areas for preservation purposes, has ironically increased the demand for tourism in these areas and thus accelerated the speed of environmental destruction.[9] Nevertheless, a sense of belonging to nature is indispensable for emotional balance. Japanese Zen Buddhism, for example, encourages deep meditation in order to achieve a sense of being at one with nature.[12] Likewise, the sounds of birdsong, buzzing insects, gently swaying leaves and the trickling of water in a forest can imprint the beauty of nature in our memory.

Wearable Forest embraces our bodies with the sense of unity with Nature through bio-acoustical interaction with wildlife in a remote forest. It enables us to experience the diversity of real ecosystems through wearable technology, regardless of the physical distance between the user and forest. Wearable Forest opens our eyes to the significance of slowing ourselves down in order to feel a sense of unity with Nature.

3.2. System Outline

Wearable Forest is a functional dress which interacts bio-acoustically with a remote forest which locates to the uninhabited subtropical forest of southern Ryukyu Islands, Japan (24°20'N, 123°55'E). It consists of an audio I/O system in a remote forest and audio-visually interactive clothing on the local side. The remote system, consisting of weather-durable microphones and speakers, is placed in the uninhabited subtropical forest of southern Ryukyu Islands. Songs of little birds, trickling sounds of streams, and insects moving about in the forest represent the diversity of organisms on the island. The audio I/O system captures and transfers the live soundscape 24 hours a day, bi-directionally between the remote forest and local system over the Internet. The system diagram is shown in Figure 2.

Figure.2 Wearable Forest System Outline

Figure.3 Clothing System Outline

As Figure 3 shows, the clothing in the local side contains two paper-thin speakers embroidered on both front shoulders(Figure 4), a matrix array of 256 pieces of white colored LEDs (Light Emitting Diodes) sewn with the conductive thread of 60 ohm resistance / 1 meter and sleeve-shaped textile sensors woven with thin wires inside the fabric. (Figure 5 and Figure 6) Electronic circuit is sewn on the inner skirt four times so as to decrease resistance for glowing LEDs. Embedded board CPU system with wireless function is mounted on the hip with a portable battery (Figure 7). The system and sewn electronics circuit are connected with standard snap. (Figure 8) The clothing design is modified twice for expressing the concept precisely. Satin textile is used for making a first prototype dress as well as soft bone used around the hem in order to keep LED away from the surface of the satin skirt for generating diffused reflection. FFT (Fast Fourier Transformation) is applied to the live soundscape data from the remote forest and each LED lighting reflects the volume of each frequency. By making the first prototype, two problems are known. The first problem is that the silhouette of the skirt does not express natural drape since the soft bone fixes the silhouette of the skirt and design of the dress does not reflect the concept of the wearable forest very well. The second problem is that the direct conversion of the live soundscape to illumination only amplifies audio information thus it does not change the quality of information at all. By reflecting on these problems, the second prototype was made (Figure 9) . To express the belonging to nature, leaf and flower cut lace is used for the inner skirt and it makes leaf and flower shadow by LED light emission. By putting lace between the electronic circuit and satin skirt, no soft bone is necessary for controlling the brightness of LED. To visualize and illuminate the bioacoustic activity contained in the remote forest soundscape as clothing fashion in real time, we proposed a Bio-Activity Index (BAI) to convert this activity into numerical data using the Internet. BAI uses Active Contour Models to quantify the bioacoustic activity of the calculated area into the shape of the visualized bio-acoustic patterns of the live soundscape data. Higher levels of bioacoustic activity are conveyed as larger LED patterns.[7](Figure 10)

In order to interact with the wildlife, users touch the textile sensor, which transfers and plays pre-recorded sounds of wildlife in real-time through speakers in the forest on the remote island.

This bio-acoustical loop of transferring live sounds bi-directionally between remote and local sides, gives the user a chance to interact with wildlife regardless of the physical distance. For instance, in the moments of quietness after a brief rain shower in the subtropical forest, the user in an urban city can remotely play back the croaking of frogs through the speaker in the forest. As a response from the forest to the sound, actual frogs might start croaking. This chorus-like experience between the user and frogs gives the user a sense of belonging with nature in an experience similar to the experience in music therapy, which is triggered by choral singing.[8]

The final prototype is shown in Figure 11.

Figure.4 Sewn Matrix Display

Figure.5 Textile Sensor and Speaker layout

Figure.6 Textile sensor
(left:1st prototype,right:2nd prototype)

Figure.7 Embedded board CPU and battery

Figure.8 Snap Connector

Figure.9 Wearable Forest Cloth
(left:1st prototype,right:2nd prototype)

Figure.10 Bio Activity Index (left:large BAI, right:small BAI)

Figure.11 Wearable Forest

3.3. Case Studies

The system was exhibited and evaluated in the Los Angeles Convention Center in Los Angeles in the United States of America over five days during SIGGRAPH 2008 and over six days during SIGMM2008 in October

2008 and in Science World British Columbia in Vancouver, Canada. During the first exhibition, the out of synchronization problem was confirmed.[6] The visitors were unable to identify a specific sound from other sounds on the audio live feed from the remote forest. This result was that the auditory signal was impossible for the user to recognize as a potential response from the wildlife, even if they actually responded to the user in the distant forest. Therefore, even if no response is transferred from the wildlife after the loopback call of the initial call, other acoustical activities in the forest are sent as believable responses, such as the sounds of birdsong, buzzing insects, gently swaying leaves and a tree falling. Those sounds indicate the non-linguistic telepresence of entities in the forest. From a psychological aspect, participants who experienced the wearable forest in the ACM SIGMM 2008 art exhibition (n=20) described “a sense of oneness” in the remote forest. They rated the episode on a number of scales meaning characteristics of transcendence such as a sense of union, and timelessness[14] . The result indicates that the Wearable Forest, HCBI interface is able to create a sense of oneness between humanity and wildlife beyond physical and genetic distance.

4. Conclusion

The potential of new expression of fashion by integrating technology and fashion was examined by showing the work of “Wearable Forest.” The new expression of fashion not only shows a novelty of surface design but also realizes fulfilment of a person’s desire and embodiment of interiority. The wearable forest aims to realize a healing cloth by taking information from remote forest using networking technology. This is an unprecedented trial to regain humanity which has been lost in the process of urbanization by information technology. In terms of regaining humanity, using a cloth as a medium has a great meaning since a cloth is the nearest interface for man. The work cannot be accomplished without the integration of fashion and technology. In the future study, it is necessary to evaluate the wearability of the cloth and revise the design of the cloth and improve sophistication as a cloth which gives the feeling of belonging to nature.

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